

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF NATURAL RESOURCES USE AND PROTECTING NATURAL ECOSYSTEMS

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Abstract: This article examines the issue of ensuring environmental stability in our country, protecting natural ecosystems by increasing the efficiency of using natural resources.

Keywords: natural resources, ecosystem, green economy, nature management, ecologization, ecology, sustainable development, innovation, resource saving.

Introduction

The main problem of nature management in our time is the increased growth of consumption and use of natural resources. On the one hand, the reason for this phenomenon is the growth of the planet's population, and on the other hand, the development of the world economy and scientific and technical progress. At the same time, large-scale pollution of the environment is increasing. The growth rate of environmental protection measures is currently lagging far behind the rate of its degradation.

As a rule, the deeper an economy is embedded in an ecosystem, the more it will exert pressure on it beyond the ecosystem's capabilities, and the more destructive such incompatibility will be.

In some literature, natural resources are understood as tools necessary for people's lives, which have a great impact on society through production forces. Since each scientist has his own research direction and theory, the term "natural resources" is expressed by many scientists in different ways.

In particular, the views of Academician I. P. Gerasimov and Professor D. L. Arman provide a perfect and detailed description of natural resources. That is, "natural resources are various means that people get directly from nature and are necessary for their life." According to another accomplished scientist, professor Y. G. Saushkin, natural resources are natural resources that can be used to obtain enough electricity for the needs of the population, produce the necessary food products, and use raw materials for industry.

The development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, including "increasing the share of electricity production using renewable and alternative energy sources from 20 percent by 2026, providing the country with a reliable,

safe, economical and efficient source of electricity, expanding production capacity" defines the tasks .

Also, regulatory and legal documents have been adopted to implement these tasks: Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 21, 2019 No. 539 "On the use of renewable energy sources"; Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 4, 2019 No. 4477 "On approval of the strategy for the transition to a "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2019-2030"; Decree of the President No. 4422 of August 22, 2019 "On operational measures to improve the energy efficiency of economic and social sectors, introduce energy-saving technologies and develop renewable energy sources" Since the beginning of 2017, the development of small and micro hydroelectric power plants in our country has reached a new level. This was reflected in the practical proposals made by the President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev on December 30, 2016 at a meeting with leading scientists of the country on the need to make serious changes in the development of renewable energy sources, especially small and micro hydroelectric power plants in our republic. "... it is necessary to cover 32% of the electricity produced in our country through hydroelectric power plants. In this regard, practical work has begun with the People's Republic of China and a preliminary agreement has been reached, for which Uzbekistan has climatic capabilities, that is, water flows. If we work in this area, we will be able to get environmentally friendly and cheap energy."

The process of modern production requires a serious strengthening of the integrated development of natural and social sciences, establishing links between them.

There are 2 types of nature management: rational and irrational. Rational nature management is a special system of enterprise activity on the use of natural energy sources. In this case, resource savings are ensured, and, consequently, the efficiency of their consumption increases, environmental protection is better ensured, including the protection of ecosystems. With irrational nature management, the operating conditions used in the system do not contribute to the implementation of these goals.

In order to preserve the integrity of the biosphere, it is necessary to take into account the laws of nature, protect and preserve the environment and rationally consume resources .

The main actions of rational use of nature:

Reduce interference with nature;

Use natural resources as little as possible without necessity;

Protect nature from pollution (do not dump pollutants into the soil and water, do not litter);

Use ecological transport;

Save water, electricity, gas;

Refuse disposable devices and goods;

Grow plants, make rational inventions, use eco-technologies .

Ensuring environmental safety and reducing environmental risks is achieved through the development and implementation of pioneering, basic innovations with an environmental focus. Environmental innovations have 2 main areas of application:

- extraction of land and water resources, as well as their more efficient use to meet the needs of society;

- protection of the environment from the harmful effects of production and human activity, from the negative effects of technological, military, socio-political and other innovations.

Here, the main principle of sustainable development is the balanced use of natural resources in economic activity, taking into account the interests of the present and future generations.

It is necessary to optimally use non-renewable natural resources and apply alternative energy sources. There is also a pressing need to develop and implement environmental innovations that allow us to eliminate and significantly reduce the negative consequences of economic activity and emerging hazards and contribute to the restoration of balance in the development of nature and society.

Continuation of negative ecological trends can lead to extremely dangerous consequences for the entire humanity and for individual countries. The world's population will increase from 7 billion to 9 billion by 2040, and the number of middle-class consumers will increase by 20 billion in the next 3 years, and the demand for resources will increase exponentially. By 2030, the world's population needs will increase by at least 50% for food, 45% for energy, and 30% for water, all at a time when environmental limits are placing new limits on broad-based economic growth. We can also expect world food prices to rise by 30-50% in real terms over the coming decades, increasing price volatility and making hundreds of millions of people worse off .

This situation is predicted to occur mainly due to population growth, but at the same time, unforeseen vagaries of nature, cruel human relations with nature,

political and biological wars and other global factors will further accelerate the process. can accelerate and worsen.

Today, the transition to environmentally sustainable development and the formation of a green economy are urgent issues, and the green economy is aimed at solving global economic and environmental problems. Green economy is a model of economic development that assumes a responsible attitude of man to the earth's resources. It aims to find a reasonable compromise between the growth of wealth and the conservation of natural resources. The basis for the formation of the concept of green economy was created at the end of the 80s of the last century within the framework of the concept of sustainable development. There are many definitions of sustainable development, but the most common and generally accepted definition is the definition proposed by the UN commission under the leadership of G. H. Brundland in 1987, which states, "Sustainable development is the meeting of the vital needs of future generations without risk." It is a development that can meet the needs of modern generations without putting them under it .

The green economy is an approach that works with the elimination of the causes of environmental problems, rather than fighting with the elimination of negative consequences. It is an economy based on "green" technologies that radically change the behavior of consumers. These include:

- energy efficiency and alternative energy;
- electrical energy management systems;
- environmentally friendly transport;
- waste, air and water waste management.

Nature is important to the heritage and culture of all humanity and must be preserved as a legacy for future generations. Living in a world with strong and healthy ecosystems provides many tangible benefits. Wildlife and natural ecosystems provide countries with stronger economies, more diverse food products, and advances in medical research.

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